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Weighted Strategies to Guide a Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm for Multi-UAV Mission Planning

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Abstract

Management and mission planning over a swarm of Unmanned Air Vehicles (UAVs) remains to date as a challenging research trend in what regards to this particular type of aircrafts. These vehicles are controlled by a number of Ground Control Stations (GCSs), from which they are commanded to cooperatively perform different tasks in specific geographic areas of interest. Mathematically the problem of coordinating and assigning tasks to a swarm of UAVs can be modeled as a Constraint Satisfaction Problem, whose complexity and multiple conflicting criteria has hitherto motivated the adoption of multi-objective solvers such as Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithms (MOEAs). The encoding approach consists of different alleles representing the decision variables, whereas the fitness function checks that all constraints are fulfilled, minimizing the optimization criteria of the problem. In problems of high complexity involving several tasks, UAVs and GCSs, where the space of search is huge compared to the space of valid solutions, the convergence rate of the algorithm increases significantly. To overcome this issue, this work proposes a weighted random generator for the creation and mutation of new individuals. The main objective of this work is to reduce the convergence rate of the MOEA solver for multi-UAV mission planning using weighted random strategies that focus the search on potentially better regions of the solution space. Extensive experimental results over a diverse range of scenarios evince the benefits of the proposed approach, which notably improves this convergence rate with respect to a naïve MOEA approach.

Keywords: Unmanned Air Vehicles, Mission Planning, Constraint Satisfaction Problems, Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm, Weighted strategies

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1. Introduction

The advent of pilot-less aerial vehicles and rapid development of their capabilities have paved the way towards new military and commercial applications. Unmanned Air Vehicles (UAVs) have become very popular in many applications including surveillance [1], training [2], disaster and crisis management [3] and firefighting [4], since they avoid risking human lives while their manageability permits to reach areas of hard access. Possibilities for UAVs span further towards the last-mile delivery of goods [5] and support for wireless communications [6, 7], among many others (see [8] for a comprehensive survey).

The process of mission planning for a collaborative swarm of UAVs involves generating tactical goals, commanding vehicles, risk avoidance, coordination and timing. Currently, UAVs are controlled remotely by human operators from Ground Control Stations (GCSs), using rudimentary planning systems, such as pre-configured plans, classical planners that are not able to cope with the entire complexity of the problem, or manually provided schedules. Classical planners are based on a graph search or resort to a logic engine. Remarkably, this kind of planners usually undergo severe practical limitations, which add to the high computational resources demanded by their underlying solvers [9]. When undertaking complex coordinated missions, planning systems demand more efficient problem-solving capabilities to cope with conflicting objectives and stringent constraints over both spatial and time domains. Therefore, the so-called Multi-UAV Cooperative Mission Planning Problems (MCMPPs) have lately gained momentum in the research community, propelled by a notable increase in the scales and number of applications foreseen for UAVs in the near future.

In the literature several algorithmic approaches have been explored and reported for UAV mission planning. Fabiani et al. [10] modelled the problem for search and rescue scenarios using Markov Decision Process (MDP) and solve it with dynamic programming algorithms. Leary et al. [11] compared the performance of Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP), Simulated Annealing (SA) and Auction Algorithms (AAs) for mission planning problems with multiple UAVs. Wang et al. [12] represented the task scheduling of UAVs as a MILP and used Tabu Search (TS) to solve this problem. Shang et al. [13] proposed a combination of Genetic Algorithms (GAs) and Ant Colony Optimizations (ACOs) for solving the UAV team oriented problems.

An essential concept in mission planning is cooperation or collaboration, which occurs at a higher level when various UAVs work together in a common mission sharing data and controlling actions together. There are few contributions that deal with Multi-UAV problems in a deliberative paradigm (cooperative task assignment and mission planning). Bethke et al. [14] proposed an algorithm for cooperative task assignment that extends the Receding-Horizon Task Assignment (RHTA) algorithm to select the optimal sequence of tasks for each UAS. Another approach by Kvarnstrom et al. [15] proposes a new mission planning algorithm for collaborative UAVs based on combining ideas from forward-chaining planning with partial-order planning. This approach led to

46 a new hybrid Partial-Order Forward-Chaining (POFC) framework that meets
47 the requirements on centralization, abstraction, and distribution found in real-
48 istic emergency services settings. Other works have been focused on distributed
49 approaches for solving collaborative mission planning. Pascarell et al. [16] pro-
50 posed a Core Paths Graph (CPG) algorithm for trajectory planning. Finally,
51 other approaches formulate the mission planning problem as a Constraint Sat-
52 isfaction Problem (CSP) [17], where the tactic mission is modelled and solved
53 using CSP techniques [18], in combination with Genetic Algorithms [19] or rep-
54 resented inside a distributed multi-agent system [20, 21].

55 Most of the above contributions assume that UAVs are commanded by a
56 single GCS, but in practice multi-UAV missions require the use of several GCSs
57 for controlling all the UAVs involved in the mission scenario. This multi-GCS
58 approach makes the underlying problem even more complex. Besides, several
59 criteria can be adopted to quantify the quality of a solution, such as the fuel
60 consumption, the makespan, the cost of the mission, or the number of UAVs or
61 GCS to employ and different risk factors that could compromise the mission,
62 among others. In these cases, the problem is considered as a Multi-Objective
63 Optimization Problem (MOP), for which an estimation of the Pareto Optimal
64 Frontier (POF) must be inferred so as to get a portfolio of solutions (mission
65 plans) differently albeit optimally balancing the considered conflicting objec-
66 tives. To this end, an algorithmic option is to use Multi-Objective Evolutionary
67 Algorithms (MOEAs), which are inspired from evolutionary reproduction and
68 mutation mechanisms to efficiently construct an estimation of the POF for a
69 given MOP. The literature is scarce in what refers to this family of multi-criteria
70 solvers when applied to multi-GCS MCMPPs, with references dealing with path
71 planning rather than mission scheduling (see e.g. [22] and references therein).

72 This manuscript extends and improves a previous approach dealing with a
73 MOEA to tackle this family of problems [19]. In this new approach, the encod-
74 ing consists of different alleles representing the features of the problem, whereas
75 the fitness function builds upon several conflicting objectives of the application
76 scenario, which are to be minimized subject to a number of constraints. Un-
77 fortunately, in some problems of high complexity involving several tasks, UAVs
78 and GCSs, where the space of search is huge compared to the space of valid so-
79 lutions, this approach is unable to converge in a reasonable time. Therefore, in
80 order to improve it and guide the algorithm to valid solutions, this work takes a
81 step further by proposing a novel *weighted random generator* for the formation
82 of new individuals. This generator is applied in three parts of the encoding:

- 83 • First, we use a weighted random function that assigns lower probability to
84 individuals with higher numbers of UAVs for performing the tasks.
- 85 • Second, the selection of the UAV(s) performing the task at hand is done by
86 using a weighted random function driven by the distance of the UAV(s) to
87 the task.
- 88 • Third, GCS controlling a UAV is selected by means of a weighted random
89 function depending on the distance of the GCS to the UAV.

90 To test this approach, several weighted strategies are proposed and assessed

91 over a number of realistic scenarios with varying scales. The obtained results
 92 are promising and encourage the adoption of the proposed simple heuristics in
 93 MOEAs applied to other multi-criteria mission planning scenarios.

94
 95 The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a baseline
 96 mathematical formulation of the considered UAV mission planning problem,
 97 including an overview of the CSPs modelling of the problem. Section 3 presents
 98 the designed solver to efficiently tackle the aforementioned problem, providing
 99 details on its encoding, constraint handling strategy and the weighted strategies
 100 used for producing and evolving individuals. Section 4 discusses the results
 101 obtained from several computer experiments using realistic data. Finally, the
 102 last section draws conclusions and outlines future research lines related to this
 103 work.

104 2. System Model and Problem Formulation

105 The MCMPP can be defined as a T -sized set of *tasks* $\mathcal{T} \doteq \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_T\}$
 106 to be performed by a swarm of U UAVs $\mathcal{U} = \{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_U\}$ within a specific
 107 time interval. Each mission should be performed in a specific geographic zone.
 108 In addition, G GCSs $\mathcal{G} \doteq \{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_G\}$ control the swarm of UAVs. A basic
 109 mission planning comprises the assignment of each task T_t (with $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$)
 110 to a specific UAV U_u (corr. $u \in \{1, \dots, U\}$), as well as each UAV to a spe-
 111 cific GCS G_g ($g \in \{1, \dots, G\}$), ensuring that the mission can be successfully
 112 performed within a time frame. Such a solution can be mathematically formu-
 113 lated as two many-to-one mapping functions $\lambda_{TU} : \{1, \dots, T\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, U\}$ and
 114 $\lambda_{UG} : \{1, \dots, U\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, G\}$ such that $\lambda_{TU}(t) = u$ and $\lambda_{UG}(u) = g$ denotes
 115 that task T_t is assigned to UAV U_u , which in turn is commanded by GCS G_g .

116 The set \mathcal{T} can collect very diverse tasks, from photographing to escorting
 117 a target, monitoring a zone or providing support for on-site communications.
 118 Some of such tasks can be performed by several UAVs (Multi-UAV), hence
 119 reducing the time needed to accomplish them, e.g. mapping an area or the so-
 120 called Step & Stare. Each task must be performed over a particular geographic
 121 area and within a specific time interval. Furthermore, tasks may require the
 122 use of sensors installed on every UAV (i.e. Electro-optical or Infra-red (EO/IR)
 123 cameras, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), Inverse Synthetic Aperture Radar
 124 (ISAR) Maritime Patrol Radar (MPR), etc.) participating in the mission. This
 125 poses further constraints to the mission planning, as it might be the case that
 126 not all UAVs in the swarm have all type of sensors installed on board, hence
 127 not being eligible to undertake any task within \mathcal{T} . This being said, UAVs
 128 performing the mission have some features that must be taken into account in
 129 order to check if a mission plan is correct:

- 130 • The initial position, in terms of Latitude (LAT) and Longitude (LONG), of the
 131 UAV U_u (with $u \in \{1, \dots, U\}$), denoted as $\text{Pos}_u(\tau) \doteq (\text{LAT}_u(\tau), \text{LON}_u(\tau))$,
 132 with τ denoting time.

- 133 • The fuel of the UAV during the mission plan, denoted as $\text{FUEL}_u(t)$ (in kilo-
- 134 grams).
- 135 • The cost per hour of usage of a UAV C_u (in monetary units per hour).
- 136 • The autonomy and range of UAV U_u , measured as the maximum flight time
- 137 T_u^{max} and distance D_u^{max} .
- 138 • The available sensors at every UAV, by which a binary correspondence $\xi : \{1, \dots, \mathbf{U}\} \times \{1, \dots, \mathbf{T}\} \mapsto \{0, 1\}$ can be built such that $\xi(u, t) = 1$ if UAV
- 139 $U_u \in \mathcal{U}$ has all sensors required to perform task $T_t \in \mathcal{T}$ installed on board,
- 140 and $\xi(u, t) = 0$ otherwise. Clearly, $\lambda_{TU}(t, u) = 0$ whenever $\xi(u, t) = 0$ (i.e.
- 141 no UAV should undertake any task for which it is unqualified). When there
- 142 is more than a sensor on-board capable of performing a given mission, the
- 143 selection of which sensor to use should be included as another design criterion
- 144 for the plan due to the direct involvement of this variable in the cost and the
- 145 autonomy of the UAV.
- 146 • $\mathbf{F} \geq 1$ flight profiles $\mathcal{F} \doteq \{F_1, \dots, F_{\mathbf{F}}\}$, each specifying speed $S_f(\tau)$, fuel
- 147 consumption rate in kilograms per hour $R_f^{\text{FUEL}}(\tau)$ and flight altitude $A_f(\tau)$ in
- 148 feet (or equivalently, ascent/descent angle) during the different time instants τ
- 149 of the profile. Since these operational parameters have direct implications on
- 150 most of the above features (e.g. fuel consumption of the UAV, its autonomy
- 151 or maximum flight time and the range or maximum flight distance), flight
- 152 profiles are also optimization variables to be assigned so as to complete the
- 153 mission plan successfully.
- 154

155 Additionally, there could exist vehicle and time dependencies between dif-

156 ferent tasks in a mission. Vehicle dependencies reflect whether two tasks can

157 be assigned to the same UAV or instead must be mapped to different UAVs,

158 i.e. whether the task-to-UAV mapping function $\lambda_{TU}(t)$ as defined above is

159 not injective. Time dependencies pose restrictions on the start and end times

160 of related tasks so they are performed simultaneously, consecutively or in any

161 other mutual relation of dependency along time. Such temporal relations can

162 be expressed in terms of the Allen's Interval Algebra [23] as follows:

- 163 • $T_t < T_{t'}$: T_t takes place before $T_{t'}$.
- 164 • $T_t m T_{t'}$: T_t meets $T_{t'}$ (i.e. $T_{t'}$ starts right after T_t).
- 165 • $T_t o T_{t'}$: T_t overlaps $T_{t'}$.
- 166 • $T_t s T_{t'}$: T_t starts jointly with $T_{t'}$.
- 167 • $T_t d T_{t'}$: T_t starts and ends while $T_{t'}$ is performed.
- 168 • $T_t f T_{t'}$: T_t finishes together with $T_{t'}$.
- 169 • $T_t = T_{t'}$: T_t is equal to $T_{t'}$.

170 Similarly, the set of GCSs controlling the deployed UAVs also feature several

171 aspects to be considered when checking a mission plan:

- 172 • The geographical position where each GCS is located, defined as $\text{Pos}_g \doteq$
- 173 $(\text{LAT}_g, \text{LON}_g)$ for $g \in \{1, \dots, \mathbf{G}\}$.
- 174 • The maximum number of UAVs that every GCS G_g can control, given by
- 175 $1 \leq \mathbf{U}_g^{max} \leq \mathbf{U}$.

- 176 • The permitted types of UAVs that every GCS can command.
- 177 • The coverage or within range of the communications equipment of every GCS,
- 178 which is assumed to be circularly shaped with radius R_g^{max} (in nautical miles).

179 Figure 1 presents a mission scenario with $T = 16$ tasks (represented as green
 180 squares and lines, and symbols as Photo or Tracking that denote a specific task
 181 to be done in that area), $U = 8$ UAVs and $G = 3$ GCSs. As shown in this
 182 figure, the zone of the mission contains several No Flight Zones (NFZs) shaded
 183 in red. These zones must be avoided in the planned trajectories of the UAVs
 184 during the mission, impacting on the duration of routes traced over the scenario
 185 and ultimately, on the fuel consumption, autonomy, range and other parameters
 related to the dynamics of the application scenario.

Figure 1: Snapshot exemplifying a mission with $T = 16$ tasks (4 of them comprising multiple UAVs), $U = 8$ UAVs and $G = 3$ GCSs.

186
 187 When a task is assigned to a vehicle, it is necessary to compute the total
 188 time taken for the UAV to complete the path between its departure location
 189 and the area where the task is to be performed. If a task T_t is the last one
 190 assigned to a vehicle U_u , the time taken to return from this last task to the
 191 base must be also calculated. In order to compute these times, it is necessary
 192 to know which of the set of UAV's flight profiles \mathcal{F} will be used, providing the
 193 fuel consumption ratio, speed and altitude as previously mentioned.

194 Furthermore, the assignment of tasks to UAV is also subject to the order in
 195 which such tasks are accomplished during the mission plan, always in compliance
 196 with the time constraints between tasks. In mathematical terms we will define

197 the mapping function $\Gamma_{TU} : \{1, \dots, T\} \times \{1, \dots, U\} \mapsto \{0, \dots, T-1\}$, which
198 establishes an order for every UAV $U_u \in \mathcal{U}$ to accomplish any given task $T_t \in \mathcal{T}$.
199 It should be clear that $\Gamma_{TU}(t, u)$ exists iff (*if and only if*) $\lambda_{TU}(t, u) = 1$, i.e.
200 UAV U_u is assigned to perform task T_t . For UAV $U_u \in \mathcal{U}$ the subset of its
201 assigned tasks will be given by $\Gamma_{U_u} = \{\Gamma_{TU}(t, u) : \lambda_{TU}(t, u) = 1\}$, such that
202 $\cup_{u=1}^U \Gamma_{U_u} = \text{Perm}(|\mathcal{T}|)$, where $\text{Perm}(a)$ denotes a permutation of the integer
203 set $\{0, \dots, a-1\}$. In addition, these orders must satisfy the time constraints
204 between any pair of tasks T_t and $T_{t'}$ (with $t \neq t'$). For example, if UAV U_1
205 performs tasks $T_1 \rightarrow T_5$, we could define $\Gamma_{U_1} = \{4, 5, 1, 3, 2\}$ such that $T_5 < T_1$
206 and $T_3 < T_2$.

Given the above definitions, a mission plan Φ can be defined as

$$\Phi \doteq [\lambda_{TU}, \Gamma_{TU}, \lambda_{UG}, \lambda_{TUF}, \lambda_{TUS}], \quad (1)$$

207 where $\lambda_{TUF} : \{1, \dots, T+1\} \times \{1, \dots, U\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, F\}$ is a mapping function
208 that establishes flight profiles to any UAV/task combination (including task
209 $T_{T+1} = \text{ReturnToBase}$); and $\lambda_{TUS} : \{1, \dots, T\} \times \{1, \dots, U\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, S\}$ simi-
210 larly indicates the sensor selection (if any) for UAV $U_u \in \mathcal{U}$ to accomplish any
211 given task $T_t \in \mathcal{T}$. It should be clear that $\lambda_{TUS}(t, u)$ exists iff (*if and only if*)
212 $\xi(u, t) = 1$, i.e. UAV U_u is qualified to undertake task T_t .

213 The quality of a given mission plan Φ is driven by the Pareto optimality of
214 a set of conflicting objectives to be simultaneously optimized:

- 215 1. The total cost of the mission $C^T(\Phi)$, given by $C^T(\Phi) = \sum_{u=1}^U C_u T_u(\Phi)$,
216 where $T_u(\Phi)$ is the total flight time of UAV u along its routes in plan Φ .
- 217 2. The end time of the mission or makespan $T^{max}(\Phi)$, i.e. the time at which
218 the last UAV $u \in \mathcal{U}$ returns to the base.
- 219 3. The risk of the mission $\delta(\Phi) \in \mathbb{R}[0, 100]$, which is computed as an average
220 percentage indicating how risky the mission is. We consider four risk factors:
221 UAVs that finish the mission with *low fuel* (with respect to a given threshold
222 FUEL^{th}), UAVs that *fly near to the ground* (depending on the route and
223 the altitude $A_f(\tau)$ of the adopted flight profile through the choice of λ_{TUF}),
224 UAVs that *fly out of the coverage or Line of Sight (LOS) of the GCSs* control-
225 ling them; and UAVs that *fly close between them*, which intuitively depends
226 on the time constraints between concurrently performed tasks and eventual
227 spatial overlaps among routes/flight profiles.
- 228 4. The number of UAVs $U^{eff} \leq U$ used in the mission plan, given by $U^{eff}(\Phi) \doteq$
229 $\sum_{u=1}^U \mathbb{I}(T_u(\Phi) > 0)$, where $\mathbb{I}(\cdot)$ is a binary function taking value 1 if its
230 argument holds (and 0 otherwise).
- 231 5. The total fuel consumption $\text{FUEL}(\Phi)$, given by the difference between the
232 initial fuel load $\sum_{u=1}^U \text{FUEL}_u(0)$ in the UAVs prior to the start of the mission
233 and that remaining $\sum_{u=1}^U \text{FUEL}_u(T^{max}(\Phi))$ once the mission is over.
- 234 6. The total flight time $T(\Phi)$, given by $\sum_{u=1}^U T_u(\Phi)$.
- 235 7. The total distance $D(\Phi)$ traversed, given by $\sum_{u=1}^U D_u(\Phi)$, where $D_u(\Phi)$ is
236 the total distance traversed by UAV u along its routes in mission plan Φ .

237 Before proceeding with the formal problem statement, some intuition must
238 be given on the confluence of the above criteria in a many-objective design

239 problem. On one hand, using many UAVs is beneficial for minimizing the total
 240 distance traversed, the makespan of the mission, yet incurs a penalty in terms
 241 of cost. On the other hand, opting for a few UAVs would yield reduced costs for
 242 the mission, but at the cost of increasing the risk of the mission. Likewise, the
 243 interplay between a moderate number of selected UAVs with the above fitness
 244 measures is unclear and stringently subject to a proper choice of the number
 245 of sensors, the order in which tasks are performed and the number of UAVs
 246 assigned to the task at hand, among many other decisions. Therefore, it is
 247 crucial to pose all these metrics in a many-objective optimization problem so as
 248 to assess their Pareto-optimal interactions.

The MCMPP problem can be then formulated as follows:

$$\text{Min}_{\Phi} \quad C^T(\Phi), T^{max}(\Phi), \delta(\Phi), U^{eff}(\Phi), \text{FUEL}(\Phi), T(\Phi), D(\Phi), \quad (2)$$

$$\text{s. t.} \quad \lambda_{TUS}(t, u) = s \text{ iff } \xi(u, t) = 1 \text{ and } \lambda_{TU}(t) = u, \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{u=1}^U \mathbb{I}(\lambda_{UG}(u) = g) \leq U_g^{max}, \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, \quad (4)$$

$$\|Pos_u(\tau) - Pos_g\|_F < R_g^{max} \text{ if } \lambda_{UG}(u) = g, \forall \tau \in [0, T^{max}(\Phi)], \quad (5)$$

$$f : \lambda_{TUF}(t, u) = f \text{ if } \lambda_{TU}(t) = u \text{ are feasible}, \quad (6)$$

$$A_f(\tau) \geq 0 \forall \tau \text{ and } \forall f \in \mathcal{F} : \lambda_{TUF}(t, u) = f \text{ if } \lambda_{TU}(t) = u, \quad (7)$$

$$\|Pos_{u_1}(\tau) - Pos_{u_2}(\tau)\|_F > 0, \forall u_1 \neq u_2 \in \mathcal{U}, \forall \tau \in [0, T^{max}(\Phi)], \quad (8)$$

$$\text{FUEL}_u(\tau) > 0, \forall \tau \in [0, T^{max}(\Phi)] \text{ if } \lambda_{TU}(t) = u \text{ for some } t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (9)$$

$$T_u(\Phi) \leq T_u^{max}, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (10)$$

$$D_u(\Phi) \leq D_u^{max}, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (11)$$

$$\Phi \text{ (through } \lambda_{TU}(\cdot) \text{ and } \Gamma_{TU}) \text{ fulfills time and vehicle constraints} \quad (12)$$

249 where Expression (3) denotes sensor constraints, i.e. a UAV assigned to a task
 250 should have the sensors needed to perform it installed on board; inequality (4)
 251 constraints the maximum number of UAVs allowed by a GCS; the inequality
 252 (5) stands for a guaranteed coverage of every UAV to the GCS to which it
 253 is allocated; the notion of feasibility in Expression (6) ensure that the UAV
 254 perform their paths for every task and in its return to the base without any
 255 incident (as will be later detailed, a Theta* algorithm [24] is used to assure
 256 that the vehicle avoids the NFZs, and that every climb/descent needed for the
 257 change of altitude is attainable); a positive distance to the ground, between
 258 different UAVs and fuel loaded at the UAVs at every time τ are reflected in
 259 inequalities (7), (8) and (9), respectively; Expressions (10) and (11) assure that
 260 the flight time and distance traversed, respectively, for each UAV do not overpass
 261 their autonomy and range; and time and vehicle dependency constraints are
 262 accounted in Expression (12).

263 2.1. CSP Modeling of the Mission Planning Problem

264 One alternative to model the above MCMPPs problem is by resorting to
 265 CSPs, since we seek the optimal schedule of resource-task assignments satisfying

266 a set of imposed constraints. Thereby, we define:

- 267 • A set of variables $\mathcal{X} = \{x_1, \dots, x_L\}$.
- 268 • For each variable, a finite set \mathcal{D}_l of possible values (its domain).
- 269 • And a set of constraints $\mathcal{C} = \{C_1, \dots, C_K\}$ restricting the values that variables
270 can simultaneously take.

271 A solution to a CSP is an assignment of a value $d_l \in D_l$ to $x_l \in \mathcal{X}$ that
272 satisfies all the imposed constraints. If all the variables have a value, then we
273 deal with a complete instantiation of the variables. Otherwise, the variables are
274 *partially* instantiated. If we assign a value to an uninstantiated variable in a
275 partial instantiation, then we *extend* the partial instantiation. We will refer to
276 an instantiation of a variable as $\langle x, v \rangle$. The projection of a constraint C_k
277 on the variables $\{x_1, \dots, x_{L'}\}$, denoted as $P(C_k, \{x_1, \dots, x_{L'}\})$, is the set of all
278 $\{v_1, \dots, v_{L'}\}$ values for which it holds that the partial instantiation $\langle x_1, v_1 \rangle$
279 $, \dots, \langle x_{L'}, v_{L'} \rangle$ can be extended to hold the constraints. When we add
280 time to the problem, then we have a Temporal Constraint Satisfaction Problem
281 (TCSP). It is a particular class of CSP where variables represent times (time
282 points, time intervals or durations) and constraints establish allowed temporal
283 relations between them [25].

284 The most widely used representation of a CSP is a graph where the pairs
285 $\langle \text{Variable}, \text{Value} \rangle$ are the nodes and the constraints are the edges. The main
286 techniques to solve CSP are:

- 287 • Search algorithms: cross the space of partial instantiations, building a com-
288 plete instantiation that satisfies all the constraints, or determine that the
289 problem is inconsistent.
- 290 • Propagation algorithms: infer new constraints that are added to the prob-
291 lem without losing any information. The worst case time complexity is
292 polynomial in the size of the problem. They are fast in discovering local
293 inconsistencies.
- 294 • Structure-driven algorithms: is a mix of the two above techniques.

295 The MCMPP is modelled as a CSP, where a graph representation of the
296 problem is presented in Figure 2. For this problem, two types of variable are
297 used: the variables of the mission plan (represented in blue in the graph), given
298 by the previous definition of Φ ; and several auxiliary variables (represented in
299 green in the graph) that are computed during the CSP propagation process and
300 employed to ease the formulation of the constraints of the problem, especially
301 those referred to time points and intervals. The different constraints of the
302 problem are represented in yellow boxes, and the optimization objectives are
303 represented in red ovals.

Figure 2: Graph representation of the CSP model. Variables of the CSP are represented in blue, Constraints in yellow, auxiliary variables in green and objectives in red.

304 The variables of the CSP are then:

- 305 • *Task Assign*: this variable corresponds to λ_{TU} in the MCMPP.
- 306 • *Orders*: this variable corresponds to Γ_{TU} in the MCMPP.
- 307 • *GCS Assign*: this variable corresponds to λ_{UG} in the MCMPP.
- 308 • *Sensor Assign*: this variable corresponds to λ_{TUS} in the MCMPP.
- 309 • *Path FP*: this variable corresponds to the first $T \cdot U$ variables $\{1, \dots, T\} \times$
 310 $\{1, \dots, U\}$ of λ_{TUF} in the MCMPP, i.e. it represents the flight profiles used
 311 in all the paths perform by UAVs for going to tasks, but not the return path.
- 312 • *Return FP*: this variable corresponds to the last U variables of λ_{TUF} in the
 313 MCMPP, i.e. it represents the flight profiles used in the `ReturnToBase` paths
 314 (i.e. the $(T + 1)$ -th task) for every UAV used in the mission.

315 On the other hand, the auxiliary variables used in the CSP model are:

- 316 • *Departure*: This variable represents the time point for each UAV/task combination
 317 when the UAV departs from its position to go to the task zone.
- 318 • *Start*: This variable represents the time point for each UAV/task combination
 319 when the UAV arrives to the task zone and starts the performance of the task.
- 320 • *End*: This variable represents the time point for each UAV/task combination
 321 when the UAV finishes the task performance.
- 322 • *Return*: This variable represents the time point for each UAV when it has
 323 returned and landed into its base position, and consequently finished its duties
 324 in the mission.
- 325 • *Duration Path, Distance Path, Fuel Cons. Path and Path Waypoints*: These
 326 variables represent, respectively, the time elapsed, the distance traversed, the
 327 fuel consumed and the waypoints followed between the departure and the
 328 start of each UAV/task combination.
- 329 • *Duration Task, Distance Task, Fuel Cons. Task and Task Waypoints*: These
 330 variables represent, respectively, the time elapsed, the distance traversed, the
 331 fuel consumed and the waypoints followed between the start and the end of
 332 each UAV/task combination.
- 333 • *Duration Return, Distance Return, Fuel Cons. Return and Return Way-*
 334 *points*: These variables represent, respectively, the time elapsed, the distance
 335 traversed, the fuel consumed and the waypoints followed between the end of
 336 the last task performed and the return for each UAV.
- 337 • *Duration Loiter*: This variable represents the time elapsed for each UAV/task
 338 combination between the end of the previous task performed by the UAV and
 339 the departure for the present task. This variable is higher than 0 when there
 340 exists some time dependencies that impede the immediate performance of the
 341 task.
- 342 • *UAV Paths*: This variable represents the waypoints followed by each UAV for
 343 the whole mission.
- 344 • *Fuel Consumptions*: This variable represents the fuel consumed by each UAV
 345 in the whole mission, i.e. $FUEL_u(0) - FUEL_u(T^{max})$.
- 346 • *Flight Times*: This variable represents the flying time of each UAV during
 347 the whole mission, i.e. T_u .

- 348 • *Distances*: This variable represents the distance traversed by each UAV in
349 the whole mission, i.e. D_u .
- 350 • *Costs*: This variable represents the cost spent for each UAV in the mission,
351 i.e. $C_u T_u$.
- 352 • *Min Distance To Ground*: This variable represents the minimum altitude
353 of each UAV to the ground (given by an elevation file) during its mission
354 flight, i.e. $\min_{\tau \in [T_u^{Climb}, T_u^{Descent}]} A_u(\tau)$, where T_u^{Climb} and $T_u^{Descent}$ represent,
355 respectively, the climb point when the UAV has reached the flight profile
356 altitude after the take-off, and the descent point when the UAV starts the
357 landing.
- 358 • *Min Distance Between UAVs*: This variable represents the minimum distance
359 between each pair of UAVs in the mission (lowest distance in all temporal
360 points), i.e. $\min_{\tau \in [0, T^{max}]} \|Pos_{u_1}(\tau) - Pos_{u_2}(\tau)\|_F$.
- 361 • *Out of GCS Coverage*: This variable represents the accumulated time for each
362 UAV where LOS is not maintain with the GCS in the mission.

363 Finally, the constraints of the CSP considered are:

- 364 • *Sensor constraints*: they check if a UAV has the sensors needed to perform its
365 assigned tasks. They are equivalent to Equation (3) in the MCMPP definition.
- 366 • *Order constraints*: they check that the orders for two different tasks assigned
367 to the same UAV are different, and lower than the number of tasks assigned
368 to that UAV, i.e. $\Gamma_{TU}(t_1, u) \neq \Gamma_{TU}(t_2, u), \forall t_1 \neq t_2 \in \mathcal{T} \forall u \in \mathcal{U}$.
- 369 • *Allen Temporal Dependencies* and *UAV Dependencies*: these constraints are
370 related to the time and vehicle dependencies mentioned previously and rep-
371 resented in Equation (12) in the MCMPP definition.
- 372 • *GCS constraints*: they assure that the GCSs assignments are correct, UAVs
373 are assigned to GCSs able to control them (*GCS-UAV Type*); GCSs do not
374 overpass their maximum number of UAV (*Max Num of UAVs per GCS*) ex-
375 pressed in Equation (4); and they are located within the GCS coverage area
376 (*Line of Sight*), expressed in Equation (5).
- 377 • *Path constraints*: these constraints assure that the UAV perform its path for
378 every UAV/task combination without any incident. In this sense, a Theta*
379 algorithm [24] is used to assure that the vehicle avoids the NFZs (*Theta**
380 *Path NFZ Avoid*), and that every climb/descent needed for the change of
381 altitude (*Climb/Descent Path*) is attainable. These constraints are part of
382 the Equation (6) in the MCMPP definition.
- 383 • *Return constraints*: they assure that each UAV perform its return to the base
384 without any incident, including NFZ avoidance (*Theta* Return NFZ Avoid*)
385 and climb/descent routes (*Climb/Descent Return*). These constraints are part
386 of the Equation (6) in the MCMPP definition.
- 387 • *Step&Stare or Task Perform*: they compute the task performance waypoints,
388 distances, durations and fuel consumptions according to the specific task, e.g.
389 Mapping tasks perform a Step&Stare over the task zone.
- 390 • *Temporal constraints*: they assure the consistency of all the times and dura-
391 tions involved in the mission planning. This includes that $start = departure +$
392 $durPath, end = start + durTask, return = end + durReturn$ and $durLoiter =$

- 393 *departure – endPrev.*
- 394 • *Overaltitude and Overspeed:* these constraints assure that the waypoints for
395 each UAV (*Final Path with Loiter*) do not overpass the speed and altitude
396 limit of the vehicle.
- 397 • *Distance to ground > 0:* these constraints assure that the vehicle does not
398 collide with the terrain. This is equivalent to Equation (7) in the MCMPP
399 definition.
- 400 • *Distance between vehicles > 0:* they assure that UAVs do not collide during
401 the mission. This is equivalent to Equation (8) in the MCMPP definition.
- 402 • *Fuel constraints ($fuel(u) < u.fuel$):* they assure that the fuel consumed by
403 each vehicle is less than its initial fuel. This is equivalent to Equation (9) in
404 the MCMPP definition.
- 405 • *Autonomy constraints ($flighttime(u) < u.autonomy$):* they assure that the
406 total flight time for each vehicle is less than its vehicle autonomy time. This
407 is equivalent to Equation (10) in the MCMPP definition.
- 408 • *Distance constraints ($distance(u) < u.range$):* they assure that the distance
409 traversed by each vehicle is less than its range. This is equivalent to Equation
410 (11) in the MCMPP definition.

411 3. Proposed Weighted-Random Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algo- 412 rithm for Mission Planning

Real-world decision problems often require the solutions to meet multiple performance criteria (or objectives) simultaneously, for which they are referred to as MOPs. Such objectives are often conflicting, wherein an improvement in one objective cannot be achieved without detriment to another objective. In this case, there is no single solution to a MOP that can be selected objectively; rather a set of solutions exists, representing different performance trade-offs between the considered criteria. A minimization MOP can be mathematically defined as follows:

$$\text{Min}_{\mathbf{x}} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = (f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_m(\mathbf{x}))^T \quad \text{subject to } \mathbf{x} \in \Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n \quad (13)$$

413 where $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)^T$ is a vector of n decision variables from the decision
414 space Ω ; $\mathbf{f} : \Omega \rightarrow \Theta \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ consists of a set of m objective functions, and a map-
415 ping from the n -dimensional decision space Ω to the m -dimensional objective
416 space Θ .

Definition 1. Given two decision vectors $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \Omega$, \mathbf{x} is said to *Pareto dominate* \mathbf{y} , denoted by $\mathbf{x} \prec \mathbf{y}$, if:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad f_i(\mathbf{x}) &\leq f_i(\mathbf{y}) \\ \exists j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad f_j(\mathbf{x}) &< f_j(\mathbf{y}) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

417 **Definition 2.** A decision vector $\mathbf{x}^* \in \Omega$, is *Pareto optimal* if $\nexists \mathbf{x} \in \Omega, \mathbf{x} \prec \mathbf{x}^*$.

Definition 3. The *Pareto set* PS , is defined as:

$$PS = \{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega | \mathbf{x} \text{ is Pareto optimal}\} \quad (15)$$

Definition 4. The *Pareto front* PF , is defined as:

$$PF = \{\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) \in \mathbb{R}^m | \mathbf{x} \in PS\} \quad (16)$$

418 The goal of Evolutionary Multi-Objective Optimization (EMO) algorithms
 419 is to evolve the non-dominated objective vectors towards PF (convergence),
 420 and also generate a good distribution of these vectors over the PF (diversity).
 421 The most used algorithm over the last decade in this field has been the Non-
 422 dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm-III (NSGA-II) [26]. NSGA-II achieves
 423 convergence and diversity by relying on two measures when comparing indi-
 424 viduals (e.g. for selection and deletion): The first is the non-domination rank,
 425 which measures how close an individual is to the non-dominated front. An indi-
 426 vidual with a lower rank (closer to the front) is always preferred to an individual
 427 with a higher rank. If two individuals have the same non-domination rank, as
 428 a secondary criterion, a crowding measure is used, which prefers individuals
 429 which are in rather deserted areas of the front. More precisely, for each indi-
 430 vidual the cuboid length is calculated, which is the sum of distances between
 431 an individual’s two closest neighbours in each dimension. The individuals with
 432 greater cuboid length are then preferred. Figure 3 shows an overview of these
 strategies.

Figure 3: NSGA-II overview of Multiobjective strategies.

433 In this approach, a previous hybrid approach based on MOEA and CSP
 434 [27] for the MCMPP is extended to consider the characteristics of the problem.
 435 The CSP is computed inside the fitness function of the MOEA, checking that
 436 solutions fulfill all the constraints. In addition, to deal with the huge search
 437 space of the problem and guide the algorithm to find valid solutions, a biased
 438 random generator has been designed for the initializer and mutation operator.
 439

440 *3.1. Encoding*

441 The encoding of this new approach consists of six different alleles represent-
 442 ing the features to be assigned in the MCMPP (presented in Section 2.1), as
 443 can be seen in Figure 4:

Figure 4: Example of an individual that represents a possible solution for a problem with 5 tasks, 3 UAVs and 2 GCSs.

- 444 1. *UAVs assigned to each task.* This allele corresponds to the *Task Assign*
 445 *variable* of the CSP model. If the T_i task is Multi-UAV, then this cell
 446 contains a vector representing the different UAVs assigned to this task, as
 447 shown in Figure 4 for tasks T_1 , T_3 and T_4 . The number of combinations,
 448 or space size, for this allele is, considering T_{MU} the number of Multi-UAV
 449 tasks, $U^{T-T_{MU}} \times (2^U - 1)^{T_{MU}}$.
- 450 2. *Flight profiles used for each UAV in the path to an assigned task.* This
 451 allele corresponds to the *Path FP variable* of the CSP model. As in the
 452 first allele, some of the cells could contain a vector if the corresponding
 453 task is performed by several UAVs. The possible values considered in this
 454 approach are *min* (Minimum consumption profile) and *max* (Maximum
 455 speed profile). The space size for this allele is $2^{T-T_{MU}} \times (2^{U+1} - 2)^{T_{MU}}$.
- 456 3. *Sensors used for the task performance* by each UAV. This allele corre-
 457 sponds to the *Sensor Assign variable* of the CSP model. These variables
 458 are necessary when the vehicle performing the task has several sensors that
 459 could perform that task. The values considered in this approach are eiS

460 (EO/IR sensor), sR (SAR radar), iR(ISAR radar) and mR (MPR radar).
 461 The space size for this allele depends on the number of sensors for each
 462 vehicle. Considering that all vehicles have s sensors, then the space size
 463 is $s^{T-TMU} \times (\sum_{i=1}^U s^i)^{TMU}$.

- 464 4. *Permutation of the task orders.* This allele corresponds to the *Orders*
 465 *variable* of the CSP model. These values indicate the absolute order of
 466 the tasks. It is only used if there are several tasks assigned to the same
 467 UAV (e.g. in Figure 4, UAV 1 performs tasks 1, 4 and 5 in this order). In a
 468 previous publication [28], it was shown that this representation, although
 469 it is not injective, is more efficient than using the orders for each pair
 470 task-UAV. The space size for this allele is $T!$.
- 471 5. *GCSs controlling each UAV.* What GCSs is assigned to monitor what
 472 UAV. This allele corresponds to the *GCS Assign variable* of the CSP
 473 model. The space size for this allele is G^U .
- 474 6. *Flight Profiles used by each UAV* to return to the base. This allele corre-
 475 sponds to the *Return FP variable* of the CSP model. The space size for
 476 this allele is 2^U .

477 The multiplication of the space sizes for each allele provides the total search
 478 space size of the problem, which shows the high complexity of adding a task,
 479 UAV or GCS to the problem.

480 In order to reduce this huge search space, some constraints have been used
 481 within the Initialization and the Mutation operator in order to assure that the
 482 solutions generated are more likely to be valid. These constraints considered
 483 are:

- 484 • *Sensor constraints:* In the task assignments, a UAV is selected if and only if
 485 it has the appropriate sensor to perform the task.
- 486 • *GCS-UAV type constraints:* In the GCS assignments, a GCS is selected for
 487 controlling a UAV if and only if the GCS is able to handle that type of vehicle.
- 488 • *Allen Temporal Dependencies:* In the order permutation, when generating
 489 the permutation, if there is some precedence or *meets* dependency, then this
 490 precedence is checked, and if not satisfied, these values are swapped in the
 491 permutation.

492 3.2. *Weighted strategies for biased random generator*

493 Usually, the first population for a MOEA is generated randomly. But some-
 494 times, in order to reduce the convergence time, if some knowledge about the
 495 problem is provided, it can be used to guide the search of solutions.

496 This information can be expressed as a high probability but not absolute
 497 certainty of (e.g. in the Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) with multiple vehicles
 498 [29, 30], it is highly probable that the best vehicle for going to a waypoint
 499 is the nearest to it in the space; but this is not always true as sometimes it
 500 implies other waypoints far from this but also near to the vehicle to remain

501 unassigned due to fuel or flight time constraints). In order to consider this kind
 502 of information appropriately, weighted strategies can be used. These strategies
 503 are used instead of the typical random generator inside the MOEA, in both
 504 creation and mutation, and assigns different probabilities for each of the possible
 505 values of the genes.

506 In this paper, three strategies are proposed to be considered:

- Arithmetic strategy: This strategy gives a lower probability to less probable values following an inverse arithmetic progression (i.e. $\frac{N-i}{N}$, with N the biggest value and i the value considered). For an integer set of N values where the bigger the value, the lower its probability, the weight for each value using the arithmetic strategy will be as follows:

$$\forall i \in 1..N, \quad weight[i] = \frac{N-i}{N} \quad (17)$$

- Harmonic strategy: This strategy gives a lower probability to less probable values following a harmonic progression (i.e. $\frac{1}{i}$, with i the value considered). For an integer set of N values where the bigger the value, the lower its probability, the weight for each value using the harmonic strategy will be as follows:

$$\forall i \in 1..N, weight[i] = \frac{1}{i} \quad (18)$$

- Geometric strategy: This strategy gives a lower probability to less probable values following an inverse geometric progression (i.e. $\frac{1}{2^i}$, with i the value considered). For an integer set of N values where the bigger the value, the lower its probability, the weight for each value using the geometric strategy will be as follows:

$$\forall i \in 1..N, weight[i] = \frac{1}{2^i} \quad (19)$$

507 These different strategies are represented in Figure 5 for a case with a maxi-
 508 mum of 5 integer values with decreasing probability. In this figure, the constant
 509 strategy represents the typical random generator, where all values have the same
 510 probability. Here, we can see that with the geometric approach, it is more likely
 511 to select value 1, while the harmonic and the arithmetic approach have lower
 512 probabilities.

Figure 5: Weighted Strategies considered with 5 integer values of decreasing probability.

513 In this approach, we have implemented a biased random generator for the
 514 formation of new individuals. This biased random generator is applied in three
 515 parts of the encoding:

- 516 • *Number of UAVs Selection (NUS)*: for Multi-UAV tasks, the selection of the
 517 number of UAVs is performed using a weighted strategy. In the previous hy-
 518 brid approach, most of the optimization objectives (except for the makespan)
 519 used as fitness function, obtained better results when the number of UAVs
 520 assigned for these tasks is low. For this reason, the new weighted random
 521 function provides a lower probability for higher numbers of UAVs.
- 522 • *Distance-based UAV Selection (DUS)*: for any task, the selection of the UAV(s)
 523 to perform it, is done through a weighted strategy dependant on the distance
 524 from the UAV(s) to the task. The closer the UAV is to the task, the higher
 525 the probability of being selected.
- 526 • *Distance-based GCS Selection (DGS)*: for any UAV, the selection of the GCS
 527 controlling it, is done through a weighted strategy dependant on the distance
 528 from the UAV to the GCS. The closer the GCS is to the UAV, the higher the
 529 probability of being selected.

530 In order to assume different orders of consistency for the selection of the
 531 UAVs number, several strategies have been proposed for the NUS weighted
 532 random function:

- 533 • Arithmetic: $\forall i = 1..U, weight[i] = \frac{U-i}{U}$
- 534 • Harmonic: $\forall i = 1..U, weight[i] = \frac{1}{i}$
- 535 • Geometric: $\forall i = 1..U, weight[i] = \frac{1}{2^i}$

536 These different strategies are represented in Figure 5 for a case with a maxi-
 537 mum of 5 UAVs. Here, we can see that with the geometric approach, it is more
 538 likely to select just 1 UAV, while the harmonic and the arithmetic approach
 539 have lower probabilities. The constant approach (uniform random function)
 540 gives the same probability to every possible number of UAVs to be used.

541 On the other hand, the same strategies have been implemented for the DUS
 542 weighted random function. However, in this case instead of the number of UAVs,
 543 the distance from each one to the task is used:

- 544 • Arithmetic: $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, weight[t, u] = \frac{\max_{j \in \mathcal{U}} \|Pos_u(0) - Pos_j\|_F - \|Pos_u(0) - Pos_t\|_F}{\max_{j \in \mathcal{U}} \|Pos_u(0) - Pos_j\|_F}$
- 545 • Harmonic: $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, weight[t, u] = \frac{1}{\|Pos_u(0) - Pos_t\|_F}$
- 546 • Geometric: $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, weight[t, u] = \frac{1}{2^{\|Pos_u(0) - Pos_t\|_F}}$

547 Finally, in a similar way, these strategies are used with the DGS weighted
 548 random function:

- 549 • Arithmetic: $\forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, weight[u, g] = \frac{\max_{j \in \mathcal{G}} \|Pos_u(0) - Pos_j\|_F - \|Pos_u(0) - Pos_g\|_F}{\max_{j \in \mathcal{G}} \|Pos_u(0) - Pos_j\|_F}$
- 550 • Harmonic: $\forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, weight[u, g] = \frac{1}{\|Pos_u(0) - Pos_g\|_F}$
- 551 • Geometric: $\forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, weight[u, g] = \frac{1}{2^{\|Pos_u(0) - Pos_g\|_F}}$

552 *3.3. Algorithm*

553 The Weighted-Random NSGA-II (WRNSGA-II) is presented in Figure 6. In
 554 this new approach, firstly a *weighted random generation of the initial popula-*
 555 *tion* is performed. Then this initial population evolves using a Multi-Objective
 556 Evolutionary Algorithm based on NSGA-II approach [26].

Figure 6: Overview of WRNSGA-II algorithm for Mission Planning.

557 The population weighted random initialisation generates a set of λ weighted
 558 random individuals, each one generated using the function presented in Algo-
 559 rithm 1. First, the number of UAVs to be used when tasks are Multi-UAV is
 560 selected (Lines 4-8) using the provided NUS strategy. Then, the concrete UAVs
 561 to be used are selected (Lines 10-14) according to the provided DUS strategy.

562 After that, the permutation orders, path flight profiles and sensors used are
563 selected randomly as usual. In Lines 20-23, it is shown how the GCSs control-
564 ling the vehicles are selected according to the DGS strategy. In this algorithm,
565 the costs computed for strategies are represented as $cNUS$, $cDUS$ and $cDGS$.
566 In both DUS and DGS, the geodesic distance function used to compute the
567 distances between tasks, vehicles and ground stations is represented as d .

Algorithm 1: WeightedRandomIndividual(M, NUS, DUS, DGS)

Input: A mission $M = (\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{G})$ where \mathcal{T} is a set of tasks to perform denoted by $\{t_1, \dots, t_T\}$, \mathcal{U} is a set of UAVs denoted by $\{u_1, \dots, u_U\}$ and \mathcal{G} is a set of GCSs denoted by $\{g_1, \dots, g_G\}$. And weighted strategies for NUS , DUS and DGS

Output: A Weighted random individual

```

1   $ind \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2  for  $t_i \in \mathcal{T}$  do
3     $num_{UAVs} \leftarrow 1$ 
4    if  $isMultiUAV(t_i)$  then
5       $cNUS \leftarrow [Strategy(j, \mathcal{U}, NUS)]_{j=1}^U$ 
6       $num_{UAVs} \leftarrow weightedRandomValue([1, 2, \dots, U], cNUS)$ 
7     $t_{assign} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
8    while  $|t_{assign}| < num_{UAVs}$  do
9       $cDUS \leftarrow [Strategy(d(t_i, u_j), \max_{u_k \in \mathcal{U}} d(t_i, u_k), DUS)]_{u_j \in \mathcal{U}}$ 
10      $t_{assign} \leftarrow t_{assign} \cup weightedRandomValue(\mathcal{U}, cDUS)$ 
11      $ind.UAV[t_i] \leftarrow t_{assign}$ 
12  $assignPermutationOrders(ind, M)$ 
13  $assignFPPaths(ind, M)$ 
14  $assignSensors(ind, M)$ 
15 for  $u_i \in \mathcal{U}$  do
16    $cDGS \leftarrow [Strategy(d(u_i, g_j), \max_{g_k \in \mathcal{G}} d(u_i, g_k), DGS)]_{g_j \in \mathcal{G}}$ 
17    $ind.GCS[u_i] \leftarrow weightedRandomValue(\mathcal{G}, cDGS)$ 
18  $assignFPReturns(ind, M)$ 
19 return  $ind$ 

```

568 For all these selections, a general Strategy function returning the cost for
569 each value has been designed (Algorithm 2), as well as a weighted random
570 function which returns a weighted random value according to the costs provided
571 (Algorithm 3).

572 The evaluation of the individuals is performed by a fitness function that first
573 checks that all the constraints of the MCMPP are fulfilled for a given solution.
574 For this, a CSP solver is used to check if the constraints are satisfied for a
575 concrete solution. When the solution is not valid according to the CSP, then
576 the number of unfulfilled constraints is returned, and used as the optimization
577 criteria with other invalid solutions. On the other hand, if all constraints are

Algorithm 2: Strategy(*value,max,strategy*)

Input: A *value* to which the concrete *strategy* must be applied, and the maximum value *max* between all possible values.

Output: The concrete cost for the value

```
1 switch strategy do
2   case Arithmetic do
3     return  $\frac{max-value}{max}$ 
4   case Harmonic do
5     return  $\frac{1}{value}$ 
6   case Geometric do
7     return  $\frac{1}{2^{value}}$ 
8   case Constant do
9     return 1
```

Algorithm 3: weightedRandomValue(*values,costs*)

Input: Vectors *V* (integer values considered) and *C* (double costs for each value) of size *d*

Output: A weighted random value based on the costs

```
1 total  $\leftarrow$  sum(C)
2 randomValue  $\leftarrow$  randomDouble()  $\cdot$  total
3 for i  $\leftarrow$  1 to d do
4   randomValue  $\leftarrow$  randomValue - Ci
5   if randomValue  $\leq$  0 then
6     return Vi
```

578 fulfilled, the fitness works as a multi-objective function minimizing the objectives
579 of the problem presented in Section 2.

580 A tournament selection is used to provide the individuals that will be chosen
581 to apply the genetic operators. The crossover operator consists of an extension
582 of the 2-point crossover and the Partially-Matched Crossover (PMX) independen-
583 tly applied to each allele of the chromosome, where a 2-point crossover is
584 applied to the 3 first alleles of size $T \cdot U$, PMX is applied to the fourth allele (the
585 permutation of orders), and another 2-point crossover is applied to the fifth and
586 sixth alleles of size U . The mutation operator is also an extension of the uni-
587 form and the insert mutation applied to each allele using the same criterion as
588 in the crossover. This *mutation operator* is *combined* with the *Biased random*
589 *generator* in order to produce new individuals based on the weighted random
590 functions previously explained.

591 Finally, the stopping criteria designed for this algorithm compares the non
592 dominated solutions obtained so far at each generation with the solutions from

593 the previous one. If the solutions from a previous generation remains unchange-
594 able for a number of generations, then the algorithm will stop and return these
595 solutions as an approximation of the POF.

596 4. Experimental Results

597 In these experiments, the main goal is to test which of the strategies pro-
598 posed (and previously defined in Section 3.3) best fits for each weighted random
599 functions (NUS, DUS and DGS) used in a particular set of Mission Planning
600 problems. The experiments are divided in two parts: first, the different NUS,
601 DUS and DGS strategies are applied and compared independently, i.e. the dif-
602 ferent NUS strategies are compared between them to get the best one, as well
603 as the different DUS and the different DGS strategies. These strategies are
604 compared against the previous approach, which is represented as the *constant*
605 *strategy*. Then, the best of these strategies for each part are selected and joined
606 to obtain the best combination of strategies. This combination is tested and
607 compared against the previous results.

608 For this purpose, a set of 16 missions of different complexity has been de-
609 signed. These datasets are presented in Table 1, where the different number of
610 tasks (and Multi-UAV tasks), UAVs, GCSs, NFZs and time dependencies are
611 shown.

612 The setup parameters of the WRNSGA-II are as follows. The selection
613 criteria ($\mu + \lambda$) used was $30 + 300$, where λ is the offspring size, and μ the
614 elitism size, i.e. the number of the best parents that survive from the current
615 generation to the next one. The mutation probability is 10%, and the number
616 of generations used in the stopping criteria is 10. Each problem is run 10
617 times, and the average and standard deviation of the hypervolume [31] of the
618 obtained solutions are calculated. The hypervolume has been computed using
619 the normalized values of the objectives variables. Moreover, the number of
620 generations needed to converge are extracted for each case.

621 For the sake of validating the statistical significance of the obtained results,
622 the distributions of the metric values obtained by the different methods on
623 each dataset have been compared by means of a nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis
624 test [32]. This test represents the nonparametric version of the classical one-
625 way ANOVA and is an extension of the Wilcoxon rank sum test to groups
626 larger than 2. To this end, the test compares the medians of the group, and
627 returns the P value for the null hypothesis that all samples are drawn from
628 the same population (or equivalently, from different populations with the same
629 distribution). If the P value is lower than a predefined α , we can infer that the
630 null hypothesis does not hold, that is, at least one sample median in the group
631 is significantly different from the others, with $(1 - \alpha)$ level of confidence, then
632 to determine which sample medians are statistically different, we have applied
633 this multiple comparison procedure with $\alpha = 0.05$ (thus, with a 95% level of
634 confidence).

635 In the first experiment, a comparative assessment of the different strate-
636 gies for the NUS weighted random function has been carried out, as shown

Table 1: Features of the different datasets designed.

Dataset Id.	Tasks	Multi-UAV Tasks	UAVs	GCSs	NFZs	Time Dependencies
1	5	0	3	1	0	0
2	6	1	3	1	1	0
3	6	1	4	2	2	1
4	7	1	5	2	1	2
5	8	2	5	2	3	1
6	9	2	5	2	0	2
7	9	2	6	2	2	2
8	10	2	6	2	3	3
9	11	3	6	2	3	2
10	12	3	7	3	0	2
11	12	3	8	3	2	3
12	13	4	7	3	4	4
13	14	4	8	3	0	3
14	15	4	9	3	5	4
15	16	4	9	3	4	4
16	16	5	10	3	5	5

637 in Table 2. These results show that the new strategies for the NUS weighted
638 random function help reducing the number of generations needed to converge
639 while maintaining the hypervolume of the solutions. Concretely, the effects of
640 these strategies are specially appreciated in datasets with a bigger number of
641 Multi-UAV tasks. The statistical significance of the results could be checked
642 through the Kruskal-Wallis test, showing a significant relevance ($p < 0.05$) for
643 the results obtained in terms of number of generations needed to converge for
644 datasets 4-9, while a significant relevance is provided for datasets 10-14 in terms
645 of hypervolume. In datasets 1, the results are quite the same for the different
646 strategies, so they are irrelevant, as datasets 2 and 3, which did not reach a sig-
647 nificance relevance through the Kruskal-Wallis test. Datasets 15 and 16, on the
648 other hand, did not reach any solution. It can be also appreciated as dataset 14,
649 which did not find any solution using the common NSGA-II (constant strategy),
650 could find solutions in some of the executions with the harmonic and geomet-
651 ric strategies. In general, the geometric strategy got better results in terms of
652 number of generations needed to converge, so we selected this strategy for the
653 NUS weighted random function.

654 We next proceed by analyzing the results of the experiments performed
655 with the different strategies for the DUS weighted random function, which are
656 presented in Table 3.

657 As can be seen, these results show that applying any of the strategies highly
658 outperformed the convergence of the algorithm due to the guidance of the search.
659 The Kruskal-Wallis test confirmed the significance relevance of the different
660 strategies compared to the common NSGA-II (constant strategy) in either terms
661 of number of generations and/or hypervolume, except for dataset 16, which did
662 not converge in any case. In the first datasets it can be appreciated that the
663 geometric strategy attains the best results, but as the complexity of the problem

Table 2: Comparative assessment of the different weighted strategies used in NUS. Results show the average \pm standard deviation for the hypervolume and the number of generations. For each dataset the best obtained result is marked in bold.

Id.	Constant Strategy		Arithmetic Strategy		Harmonic Strategy		Geometric Strategy	
	Hypervol.	No. Gen.	Hypervol.	No. Gen.	Hypervol.	No. Gen.	Hypervol.	No. Gen.
1	$0.80 \pm 1e^{-6}$	41 ± 6	$0.80 \pm 1e^{-6}$	46 ± 7	$0.80 \pm 1e^{-6}$	41 ± 5	$0.80 \pm 1e^{-6}$	44 ± 7
2	$0.72 \pm 1e^{-3}$	253 ± 19	$0.72 \pm 2e^{-3}$	243 ± 25	$0.72 \pm 1e^{-3}$	231 ± 23	$0.72 \pm 3e^{-3}$	233 ± 17
3	0.69 ± 0.01	395 ± 26	0.68 ± 0.03	382 ± 27	0.69 ± 0.01	368 ± 30	0.69 ± 0.02	363 ± 25
4	0.74 ± 0.02	593 ± 46	0.74 ± 0.03	578 ± 35	0.73 ± 0.04	543 ± 37	0.74 ± 0.01	537 ± 21
5	0.68 ± 0.04	408 ± 32	0.67 ± 0.06	393 ± 36	0.68 ± 0.03	376 ± 29	0.69 ± 0.02	370 ± 31
6	0.63 ± 0.04	697 ± 38	0.63 ± 0.04	654 ± 39	0.63 ± 0.05	626 ± 36	0.63 ± 0.03	601 ± 38
7	0.57 ± 0.08	865 ± 41	0.57 ± 0.07	812 ± 39	0.57 ± 0.08	777 ± 36	0.57 ± 0.07	759 ± 37
8	0.40 ± 0.10	968 ± 31	0.42 ± 0.08	928 ± 35	0.43 ± 0.10	880 ± 33	0.43 ± 0.08	846 ± 26
9	0.26 ± 0.12	1000 ± 1	0.31 ± 0.14	998 ± 3	0.33 ± 0.13	976 ± 15	0.33 ± 0.11	951 ± 18
10	0.15 ± 0.08	1000 ± 0	0.23 ± 0.14	1000 ± 1	0.26 ± 0.10	997 ± 2	0.28 ± 0.09	992 ± 4
11	0.05 ± 0.06	1000 ± 0	0.12 ± 0.10	1000 ± 0	0.19 ± 0.09	1000 ± 0	0.24 ± 0.04	1000 ± 0
12	$1e^{-3} \pm 2e^{-3}$	1000 ± 0	0.03 ± 0.01	1000 ± 0	0.05 ± 0.01	1000 ± 0	0.11 ± 0.06	1000 ± 0
13	$2e^{-5} \pm 3e^{-5}$	1000 ± 0	$3e^{-3} \pm 3e^{-4}$	1000 ± 0	$0.01 \pm 6e^{-3}$	1000 ± 0	0.06 ± 0.01	1000 ± 0
14	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	$2e^{-3} \pm 7e^{-4}$	1000 ± 0	$0.01 \pm 2e^{-3}$	1000 ± 0
15	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0
16	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0

Table 3: Comparative assessment of the different weighted strategies used in DUS. Results show the average \pm standard deviation for the hypervolume and the number of generations. For each dataset the best obtained result is marked in bold.

Id.	Constant Strategy		Arithmetic Strategy		Harmonic Strategy		Geometric Strategy	
	Hypervol.	No. Gen.	Hypervol.	No. Gen.	Hypervol.	No. Gen.	Hypervol.	No. Gen.
1	$0.80 \pm 1e^{-6}$	41 ± 6	$0.80 \pm 2e^{-6}$	40 ± 6	$0.80 \pm 1e^{-6}$	39 ± 5	$0.80 \pm 2e^{-6}$	39 ± 6
2	$0.72 \pm 1e^{-3}$	253 ± 19	$0.72 \pm 2e^{-3}$	249 ± 25	$0.72 \pm 1e^{-3}$	240 ± 23	$0.72 \pm 3e^{-3}$	238 ± 17
3	0.69 ± 0.01	395 ± 26	0.69 ± 0.02	366 ± 24	0.69 ± 0.01	354 ± 18	0.68 ± 0.03	345 ± 17
4	0.74 ± 0.02	593 ± 46	0.73 ± 0.04	566 ± 29	0.74 ± 0.02	531 ± 33	0.73 ± 0.02	519 ± 25
5	0.68 ± 0.04	408 ± 32	0.68 ± 0.05	365 ± 30	0.67 ± 0.03	351 ± 26	0.64 ± 0.02	342 ± 25
6	0.63 ± 0.04	697 ± 38	0.62 ± 0.03	621 ± 29	0.63 ± 0.04	572 ± 41	0.61 ± 0.03	539 ± 63
7	0.57 ± 0.08	865 ± 41	0.57 ± 0.07	789 ± 40	0.56 ± 0.08	751 ± 34	0.51 ± 0.11	710 ± 72
8	0.40 ± 0.10	968 ± 31	0.43 ± 0.08	879 ± 37	0.44 ± 0.10	848 ± 32	0.40 ± 0.13	825 ± 69
9	0.26 ± 0.12	1000 ± 1	0.40 ± 0.10	975 ± 15	0.42 ± 0.09	929 ± 45	0.38 ± 0.15	903 ± 89
10	0.15 ± 0.08	1000 ± 0	0.29 ± 0.09	996 ± 3	0.33 ± 0.10	972 ± 12	0.29 ± 0.15	921 ± 78
11	0.05 ± 0.06	1000 ± 0	0.19 ± 0.10	1000 ± 0	0.25 ± 0.08	1000 ± 0	0.21 ± 0.13	956 ± 98
12	$1e^{-3} \pm 2e^{-3}$	1000 ± 0	0.12 ± 0.12	1000 ± 0	0.19 ± 0.07	986 ± 69	0.15 ± 0.13	936 ± 123
13	$0 \pm 3e^{-5}$	1000 ± 0	0.04 ± 0.01	1000 ± 0	0.10 ± 0.02	972 ± 54	0.06 ± 0.01	902 ± 92
14	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	$5e^{-3} \pm 4e^{-3}$	997 ± 25	0.02 ± 0.01	982 ± 68	$0.03 \pm 4e^{-3}$	897 ± 142
15	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	$1e^{-3} \pm 4e^{-3}$	967 ± 101	$0.01 \pm 2e^{-3}$	902 ± 168
16	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0	0 ± 0	1000 ± 0

664 increases, the hypervolume for this strategy gets lower, probably due to local
665 minima. For this purpose the harmonic strategy gets better results, so it will
666 be regarded as the best-performing strategy for the final experiment.

667 Then, we consider the DGS weighted random function. The results of the ex-
668 periments performed with the different strategies for this function are presented
669 in Table 4.

670 In this case, the behaviour is similar to DUS strategies, where the geometric
671 strategy is better for the first datasets, but for more complex datasets, it gets
672 stuck in local minima. The Kruskal-Wallis test is once more applied to confirm

Table 4: Comparative assessment of the different weighted strategies used in DGS. Results show the average \pm standard deviation for the hypervolume and the number of generations. For each dataset the best obtained result is marked in bold.

Id.	Constant Strategy		Arithmetic Strategy		Harmonic Strategy		Geometric Strategy	
	Hypervol.	No. Gen.	Hypervol.	No. Gen.	Hypervol.	No. Gen.	Hypervol.	No. Gen.
1	$0.80 \pm 1e^{-6}$	41 \pm 6	$0.80 \pm 2e^{-6}$	44 \pm 5	$0.80 \pm 1e^{-6}$	42 \pm 6	$0.80 \pm 1e^{-6}$	45 \pm 5
2	$0.72 \pm 1e^{-3}$	253 \pm 19	$0.72 \pm 1e^{-3}$	256 \pm 15	$0.72 \pm 3e^{-3}$	251 \pm 18	$0.71 \pm 2e^{-3}$	255 \pm 20
3	0.69 \pm 0.01	395 \pm 26	0.68 ± 0.01	390 \pm 20	0.69 ± 0.02	388 \pm 17	0.69 ± 0.02	383 \pm 18
4	0.74 ± 0.02	593 \pm 46	0.74 \pm 0.01	591 \pm 40	0.74 ± 0.02	573 \pm 38	0.74 ± 0.01	560 \pm 31
5	0.68 ± 0.04	408 \pm 32	0.68 \pm 0.03	398 \pm 34	0.68 ± 0.04	385 \pm 36	0.67 ± 0.04	379 \pm 27
6	0.63 ± 0.04	697 \pm 38	0.63 \pm 0.03	676 \pm 38	0.63 ± 0.04	641 \pm 36	0.62 ± 0.02	620 \pm 43
7	0.57 ± 0.08	865 \pm 41	0.57 ± 0.06	812 \pm 35	0.57 \pm 0.06	795 \pm 40	0.55 ± 0.07	778 \pm 55
8	0.40 ± 0.10	968 \pm 31	0.41 ± 0.10	938 \pm 36	0.43 \pm 0.09	901 \pm 40	0.42 ± 0.10	889 \pm 47
9	0.26 ± 0.12	1000 \pm 1	0.30 ± 0.09	983 \pm 9	0.32 \pm 0.08	962 \pm 15	0.30 ± 0.10	946 \pm 30
10	0.15 ± 0.08	1000 \pm 0	0.26 ± 0.09	998 \pm 2	0.29 \pm 0.08	986 \pm 9	0.26 ± 0.11	942 \pm 56
11	0.05 ± 0.06	1000 \pm 0	0.17 ± 0.10	1000 \pm 0	0.21 \pm 0.09	1000 \pm 0	0.19 ± 0.11	976 \pm 89
12	$1e^{-3} \pm 2e^{-3}$	1000 \pm 0	0.09 ± 0.06	1000 \pm 0	0.13 \pm 0.08	1000 \pm 0	0.10 ± 0.10	967 \pm 102
13	$0 \pm 3e^{-5}$	1000 \pm 0	$0.02 \pm 8e^{-3}$	1000 \pm 0	0.07 \pm 0.01	1000 \pm 0	$0.03 \pm 5e^{-3}$	938 \pm 103
14	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0
15	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0
16	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	1000 \pm 0

673 the significance relevance of the different strategies compared to the common
674 NSGA-II in either terms of number of generations and/or hypervolume, showing
675 relevance in datasets 5-13. So, as before, the harmonic strategy gets better
676 results for more complex datasets, so it will be taken as the better strategy for
677 the final experiment.

678 In the final experiment, we took the best strategies obtained in the previous
679 experiments (geometric for NUS, harmonic for DUS and harmonic for DGS)
680 and used the all together in the algorithm. The results obtained are shown
681 in Table 5, where the average, standard deviation and p-value obtained in the
682 Kruskal-Wallis test (in comparison with the common NSGA-II approach with
683 no strategies applied) are presented for both the hypervolume obtained and the
684 number of generations needed to converge.

685 These results show a notable improvement in the reduction of the number
686 of generations needed to converge for complex datasets, which reflect an in-
687 creased convergence rate. In addition, some valid solutions were obtained for
688 dataset 16, where other approaches did not reach any solution. As the stopping
689 criteria used for convergence checks that the non-dominated solutions obtained
690 remain unchangeable for 10 generations, it is common that for the most complex
691 datasets, with a lot of solutions in the POF, the algorithm did not reach the
692 complete POF before the 1000 generations limit.

693 As there are 7 objectives to optimize, in order to visualize the form of the
694 Pareto fronts obtained for each dataset, a Parallel Coordinates Visualization [33]
695 has been used to represent the solutions obtained. For instance, in Figure 7,
696 the Parallel Coordinates Visualization for dataset 4 is presented, where we can
697 clearly distinguish several sets of solutions that have been clustered in different
698 colors. In blue, it is appreciable that there are some solutions that have a
699 high makespan, but instead have low values for the rest of variables. The red

Table 5: Results (average / standard deviation / Kruskal-Wallis p-value) obtained with the best combination of strategies (geometric NUS, harmonic DUS and harmonic DGS).

Id.	Hypervolume	No. Generations
1	$0.80/1e^{-6}/0.76$	39/7/0.31
2	$0.71/4e^{-3}/0.56$	203/12/0.06
3	$0.69/0.03/0.65$	274/21/0.03
4	$0.74/0.02/0.54$	486/24/0.04
5	$0.68/0.05/0.48$	334/29/0.03
6	$0.63/0.02/0.45$	519/37/0.03
7	$0.56/0.10/0.54$	703/41/0.04
8	$0.48/0.09/0.41$	808/34/0.04
9	$0.51/0.08/0.36$	876/31/0.03
10	$0.36/0.09/0.09$	916/26/0.04
11	$0.28/0.12/0.05$	987/9/0.02
12	$0.31/0.07/0.04$	$998/3/4e^{-3}$
13	$0.26/0.03/0.04$	$1000/1/7e^{-5}$
14	$0.29/0.01/0.04$	1000/0/1.0
15	$0.16/5e^{-3}/0.04$	1000/0/1.0
16	$0.06/5e^{-3}/0.04$	1000/0/1.0

700 solutions are similar, but decreasing the makespan value while increasing the
701 others except for the risk, fuel and number of UAVs, which remain the lowest.
702 Green solutions have the highest values for cost, flight time and distance, while
703 preserving a medium value for makespan, fuel, risk and number of UAVs. Purple
704 solutions present the highest values for fuel and risk, but have the lowest values
705 for makespan. Orange solutions also have low values for makespan and high
706 values for risk and number of UAVs, while the rest of variables have medium-
707 high values. Finally, brown and yellow solutions have medium values for most
708 variables, except for risk in some cases.

709 As the complexity of the problem increases, there are more non-dominated
710 solutions and most times they are more scattered, so the visualization becomes
711 harder. For example, Figure 8 shows the Parallel Coordinates Visualization for
712 dataset 9. Here, it is more difficult to appreciate sets of solutions. In blue, some
713 solutions with low cost, fuel and distance, but high risk and medium number
714 of UAVs are represented. Green solutions present a high value for fuel, while
715 maintaining low values for flight time and number of UAVs. Yellow solutions
716 present a low number of UAVs but a high risk. Purple solutions have high
717 cost, flight time and distance, but low risk. Red solutions have the highest
718 makespan, while orange solutions have the lowest, but the rest of variables are
719 very scattered for these solutions.

720 In these cases, sometimes is useful to use another type of visualization, such
721 as Radial Visualization (RadViz) [34], in order to visualize the clusterization of
722 the solutions. The RadViz plot for dataset 9 can be seen in Figure 9, maintaining
723 the same colors used in Figure 8. In this plot, we can see that the same solutions
724 clustered in the Parallel Coordinates approach are grouped together in RadViz
725 (except for pink solutions, which represent the remaining solutions that were not

Figure 7: Parallel Coordinates Visualization of the solutions obtained for dataset 4.

Figure 8: Parallel Coordinates Visualization of the solutions obtained for dataset 9.

726 clustered). In this visualization, we can appreciate how some sets of solutions
 727 approach to some objectives (when they have higher values) while they keep
 728 away from others (when they have lower values), e.g. blue solutions are very
 729 close to Risk and Number of UAVs, because these solutions are worse for these
 730 variables, while they stay far from the rest of variables, were they performed
 731 better. In this sense, the solutions more centered in the graph, represent the

732 ones having middle values for most variables, e.g. some pink solutions and the
 733 purple solutions. On the other hand, the yellow solutions keep away from the
 734 Number of UAVs, which are better optimized, but we can appreciate how some
 735 of them stay close to the cost, while other approach to the makespan, because
 736 they get different results in these two variables. Besides, the red solutions clearly
 737 approach the makespan, were they have the biggest value for this variable. It
 738 can be noticed that some color/solution pair sets are merged together, such
 739 as yellow and green solutions, or orange and brown solutions. This is due to
 740 the big similarities between these groups, were only one or two variable behave
 741 differently, and usually these variables still remain close, with no big numeric
 742 difference between them, e.g. green and yellow are mostly similar except for
 743 some yellow solutions that get better results in terms of fuel and cost, while
 744 green solutions do not.

Figure 9: Radial Visualization (RadViz) of the solutions obtained for dataset 9.

745 With the combination of these two visualization methods, we can conclude
 746 that for complex datasets, as dataset 9, where there is a big number of solutions
 747 and they are highly sparsed, it is possible to appreciate some behaviors in terms
 748 of clustering of solutions, although most of these clusters are merged between
 749 them.

750 5. Conclusions

751 In this paper we have presented a new Weighted Random MOEA-CSP ap-
 752 proach for solving the Multi-UAV Mission Planning Problem. The presented
 753 approach considers missions consisting of several tasks to be performed by sev-
 754 eral UAVs using a specific sensor. Each UAV is controlled by a GCS and use

755 specific Flight Profiles. The problem has been modelled as a CSP where the
756 encoding of the MOEA considers the same variables as the CSP. Thereby, the
757 fitness function can use the CSP to check if solutions are valid, and then a
758 multi-objective fitness function optimizing several objectives is considered.

759 In addition, a biased random generator has been designed in order to guide
760 the generation of new individuals. This generator improves the selection of the
761 number of UAVs for Multi-UAV tasks, and the selection of the UAV based on the
762 distance to the task. For each selection, three strategies (arithmetic, harmonic
763 and geometric) have been proposed to be used as weighted random functions.

764 The experiments performed over several missions show that this new ap-
765 proach outperforms the results obtained previously in terms of increased con-
766 vergence rate. In addition, when the scenario of the mission is not favourable for
767 the proposed weighted random approach, we obtain similar results to the pre-
768 vious approach. Moreover, this approach has resulted very helpful for problems
769 of big complexity where convergence is difficult.

770 The main lack in this approach is the huge number of solutions obtained
771 when missions are complex, which makes it difficult to select the final solution
772 to be executed by the operator. Future works will focus on developing a Decision
773 Support System (DSS) for this problem, in order to select a few solutions among
774 those obtained by the algorithm according to some quality metrics and the GCS
775 operator profile.

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